

ASSESSMENT OF KORONADAL NATIONAL COMPREHENSIVE HIGH SCHOOL SPECIAL PROGRAM IN SPORTS: BASIS FOR A PROPOSED ENHANCEMENT DEVELOPMENT PLAN

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ABSTRACT

This action research assessed the implementation of the Special Program in Sports (SPS) at Koronadal National Comprehensive High School to determine how effectively it addresses the needs of talented students across various sports disciplines and promotes their academic, personal, and social development. Guided by the view that schools are ideal settings for youth sport development, the study employed a descriptive–evaluative research design. Data were gathered through surveys, interviews, and document analysis involving teachers, students, and program implementers. A SWOT (Strengths, Weaknesses, Opportunities, and Threats) analysis was utilized to systematically examine internal and external factors affecting the SPS, particularly the emerging gap between teachers and learners in the teaching–learning process. The analysis process focused on identifying program strengths to be sustained and weaknesses to be addressed through strategic planning. Findings revealed that the SPS positively contributed to students’ self-control, effort, teamwork, and overall engagement, supporting prior studies on sport-based development programs. However, challenges related to instructional alignment, communication, and resource limitations were also identified, which may hinder the school’s goal of providing quality education. Based on the results, a development plan was proposed to enhance program strengths and mitigate identified weaknesses. The study concludes that with targeted interventions and systematic planning, the SPS can better fulfill its role as a tool for holistic youth development and educational advancement.

Keywords: *Special Program in Sports, Action Research, SWOT analysis, School-based Sports Program, Youth Development, Program Evaluation*

INTRODUCTION

Schools play a vital role in fostering positive youth development through structured physical education and sport programs. Physical education and school-based sports initiatives have been shown to generate multiple benefits for learners, including improved physical health, enhanced academic engagement, and positive social behaviors. Bailey (2006) emphasized that participation in school sports contributes not only to physical fitness but also to cognitive, affective, and social development when programs are purposefully designed and aligned with educational objectives. These outcomes support the growing recognition of sport as a meaningful educational tool rather than a purely recreational activity.

The concept of positive youth development through sport highlights the importance of intentional program design and supportive learning environments. Coakley (2011) explained that youth sports promote positive development only when they are structured to prioritize learning, inclusion, and personal growth rather than competition alone. Similarly, Weiss and Wiese-Bjornstal (2009) noted that physical activity programs emphasizing enjoyment, mastery, and social connection are more likely to foster psychosocial outcomes such as confidence, motivation, and emotional regulation among young participants.

Research further indicates that sport-based youth development programs can effectively cultivate life skills transferable beyond athletic settings. Fraser-Thomas et al. (2005) found that well-implemented youth sport programs promote personal and social competencies such as leadership, responsibility, and cooperation. These programs provide opportunities for young people to develop self-discipline and resilience through structured participation and guided reflection. Complementing this perspective, Bean et al. (2016) highlighted that life skill development in sport is most effective when instructors deliberately integrate learning experiences that encourage goal setting, communication, and teamwork.

Recent studies also emphasize that consistent engagement in structured sports programs can strengthen students' academic motivation and school attachment, as well as reduce risky behaviors (Danish et al., 2005). By providing structured opportunities for achievement and social support, sports programs foster not only personal growth but also positive relationships with peers and mentors, which are critical for holistic development. This perspective underscores the importance of evaluating programs like the Special Program in Sports (SPS) to ensure that athletic training is effectively integrated with educational and psychosocial goals.

One influential framework supporting life skills and character development through sport is the Teaching Personal and Social Responsibility (TPSR) model. Hellison (2011) proposed that physical activity settings can be powerful contexts for teaching respect,

effort, self-direction, leadership, and caring for others. The TPSR model emphasizes the role of teachers and coaches in creating supportive environments where learners are encouraged to take responsibility for their actions and contribute positively to the group.

Extending the TPSR framework, Martinek and Hellison (2016) emphasized the importance of leadership development in youth sport and physical education. They argued that sport provides authentic opportunities for students to practice leadership behaviors such as decision-making, communication, and peer support. When educators intentionally guide these experiences, students are more likely to transfer leadership skills learned in sport to academic and social contexts.

Overall, the reviewed literature underscores the potential of school-based sports programs to serve as effective platforms for holistic youth development when they are intentionally structured, well-supported, and aligned with educational goals. These findings provide a strong theoretical and empirical foundation for evaluating specialized programs such as the Special Program in Sports (SPS). By assessing SPS implementation through a school-based diagnostic framework, the present study seeks to contribute to the existing body of literature by identifying strategies that strengthen program effectiveness and promote positive developmental outcomes among learners.

Research Questions

This action research aimed to assess the Special Program in Sports of Koronadal National Comprehensive High School. Specifically, it aimed to:

1. To determine the Profile of the Special Program in Sports at Koronadal National Comprehensive High School in terms of the following Key Performance Indicators (KPIs):
 - 1.1 Enrollment Rate;
 - 1.2 Drop-out Rate;
 - 1.3 Graduation Rate;
 - 1.4 Transferred to regular class.
2. To determine the internal and external factors affecting the implementation Special Program in Sports at Koronadal National Comprehensive High School.
3. To develop a proposed enhancement development plan based on the results of the study.

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

This study employed a mixed-methods action research design, integrating both quantitative and qualitative approaches to comprehensively assess the implementation of the Special Program in Sports (SPS). The quantitative component focused on the analysis of school records, specifically enrollment, dropout, graduation, and transfer rates of SPS learners, to determine participation trends and program outcomes. The qualitative

component utilized interview guide questionnaires and focus group discussions (FGDs) to capture in-depth perspectives of teachers and students regarding program implementation, challenges, and strengths. The combination of these methods enabled triangulation of data and provided a more holistic understanding of the SPS.

Locale of the Study

The study was conducted in a public secondary school offering the Special Program in Sports located in Koronadal City, Philippines. To comply with ethical considerations, the name of the institution is not disclosed, as formal permission for identification was not obtained. The school caters to junior and senior high school students and implements SPS across various sports disciplines.

Participants and Other Sources of Data

The respondents of the study consisted of SPS students and teachers. For the quantitative data, school records on enrollment, graduates, dropouts, and students transferred to the regular program were obtained from the school records office. For the interview guide questionnaire, a total of twenty (20) respondents were selected, composed of ten (10) randomly selected SPS honor students and ten (10) SPS teachers. In addition, ten (10) SPS teachers were purposively selected to participate in the focus group discussion based on their direct involvement and experience in implementing the program.

A non-probability sampling technique, specifically purposive sampling, was employed in selecting the teacher-participants for the qualitative phase. This sampling method allowed the researchers to intentionally choose respondents who could provide rich and relevant information aligned with the objectives of the study.

Research Instruments

The primary research instruments used were a researcher-made interview guide questionnaire and a focus group discussion guide. The interview guide questionnaire consisted of structured and semi-structured questions designed to gather respondents' perceptions of the SPS in terms of implementation, teaching–learning processes, and observed outcomes. The instrument contained 15 items using a Likert-type scale for selected questions and open-ended items to elicit qualitative insights. The focus group discussion guide included 10 open-ended questions that facilitated collaborative discussion among teacher-participants regarding strengths, weaknesses, opportunities, and threats affecting the SPS. The instruments were reviewed by experienced educators for content clarity and relevance prior to administration.

Data Gathering Procedure

Prior to data collection, an approval letter was secured from the school head. Upon approval, the researchers administered the interview guide questionnaires to the selected participants, allowing sufficient time for completion. Confidentiality and voluntary participation were emphasized, and respondents' identities were kept anonymous. All

twenty (20) questionnaires were fully answered and retrieved. After consolidating and reviewing the questionnaire responses, the researchers conducted a focus group discussion with the ten (10) purposively selected SPS teachers using the validated FGD guide. The discussion was facilitated by the researchers and documented for analysis.

Data Analysis

Quantitative data obtained from school records were analyzed using descriptive statistics, such as frequency counts and percentages, to determine trends in enrollment, dropout, graduation, and transfer rates. Qualitative data from the interview questionnaires and FGDs were analyzed using thematic analysis. Responses were transcribed, coded, and grouped into emerging themes, which were then examined using a SWOT (Strengths, Weaknesses, Opportunities, and Threats) framework to guide program evaluation and development planning.

Scope and Limitations of the Study

This study focused solely on the assessment of the Special Program in Sports in one public secondary school and involved a limited number of SPS students and teachers. The findings are therefore context-specific and may not be generalized to other schools offering SPS. Data were based on self-reported perceptions and existing school records, which may be subject to respondent bias and record limitations. Despite these constraints, the study provides valuable insights into the implementation of SPS and serves as a basis for program improvement and future research.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Figure 1.1 Rates of Enrolees of SPS Students in Koronadal National Comprehensive High School

The Figure 1.1 shows the rate of SPS enrolees for the years' 2016, 2017, and 2018. Based on the Graph there are 42 (30%) students who enrolled in the year 2016, 48 (32%) on year 2017, and 52 (38%) on the year 2018. The graph shows that there is an increase of enrolees every year in the SPS program.

Figure 1.2 Rate of Dropouts of SPS Students in Koronadal National Comprehensive High School

Figure 1.2 shows that there is no record of SPS drop-out rate for the school years' 2016, 2017, and 2018. Those students who failed to pass the standard of SPS are transferred to the athlete section where in even though they are not in the program they will still be able to continue as an athlete, some of them transferred out.

Figure 1.3 Rate of Graduates of SPS Students in Koronadal National Comprehensive High School

The Figure 1.3 shows the rate of SPS Graduate for the years' 2016, 2017, and 2018. Based on the Graph there are 40 (98%) students who graduated in the year 2016, 36 (86%) on year 2017, and 38 (88%) on the year 2018. The number of Graduates are not the same every year because some failed to pass the standards of the SPS program.

Figure 1.4 Rate of Transferred Student to other program of SPS Students in Koronadal National Comprehensive High School

The figure 1.4 shows the number of students who are transferred to the regular program from the SPS. For 2016 2 (7%) students failed to pass the standard, in 2017 there are 12 (43%) students and on 2018 a total of 14 (50%) students who are transferred.

Table 1.1 SWOT analysis of SPS of Koronadal National Comprehensive High School

S	W	O	T
Strengths	Weaknesses	Opportunities	Threats
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Qualified Teachers • Highly Trained Coaches • Multi-Disciplinary team • Specific Sports Training 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Not Enough Equipment • Lack of some Facilities • Delayed Trainings • Lack of Internal Communication 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Sports Scholarships from other School • Seminars for Coaches by DepEd • Sports training Endorsement • Donations of Sports Equipment 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Other Schools are Scouting • Other Schools Offer Sports Track • Other schools has complete Facilities

Table 1.1 present the different responses of teachers and students in terms of strengths, weaknesses, opportunities and threats in Special Program in Sports. The researchers come up with the SWOT analysis in the second column based from the responses of the teachers and students. The data was gathered through focus group discussion and interview guides. This shows that the strengths of the Special Program in Sports are “Qualified Teachers”, “Highly Trained Coaches”, “Multi- Disciplinary team” and “Specific Sports Training”. The weaknesses are “Not Enough Equipment’s”, “Lack of some Facilities”, “Delayed Trainings”, and “Lack of Internal Communication”. The opportunities are “Sports Scholarships from other School”, “Invitational Games”, “Sports training Endorsements” and “Donations of Sports Equipment’s”. And the possible threats are “Other Schools are scouting”, “Few Schools Offer Sports Track” and “Other schools has complete Facilities”.

Table 1.2 SWOT analysis of SPS of Koronadal National Comprehensive High School and Juxtaposition

		S	W
 INTERNAL FACTORS		S1. Qualified Teachers S2. Highly Trained Coaches S3. Multi- Disciplinary team S4. Specific Sports Training.	W1. Not Enough Equipment W2. Lack of some Facilities W3. Delayed Trainings W4. Lack of Internal Communication.
 EXTERNAL FACTORS			
O	O1. Sports Scholarships from other School O2. Seminars for Coaches by DepEd O3. Sports training Endorsement O4. Donations of Sports Equipment.	S4-O3: Strengthening partnership with LGU for continuous improvement of athletes. S1&S2-O2: Coaching seminars intensification for teachers who are coaching.	W1-O4: Maximizing stakeholders supports in the acquisition of sports equipment. W3-O1: Intensification of trainings through partnership with private institutions offering Sports Scholarships program.
T	T1. Other Schools are Scouting T2. Other Schools Offer Sports Track T3. Other schools has complete Facilities. (Swimming pool, Lawn Tennis court).	S3-T2: Sports Training Intensification to Prevent students from transferring to other schools. S4- T3: improving internal communication to the LGU's to prevent potential athletes from transferring to the other school.	W1&W2-T3: Provision of adequate sports facilities and equipment. W4-T1: Improving internal communication system to prevent potential athletes from transferring to other school.

Table 1.2 shows the result of juxtaposition between the internal to external factors of the SPS. This figure also illustrates the database.

Juxtaposition is a literary device wherein the author places a person, concept, place, idea, or theme parallel to each other. The purpose of juxtaposing two directly or indirectly related entities close together in literature is to highlight the contrast between the two and compare them.

Conclusions

This action research examined the effectiveness of the Special Program in Sports (SPS) in addressing the academic and developmental needs of student-athletes through a SWOT analysis. Consistent with previous studies, the findings affirm that sport-based development programs with trained instructors and structured activities contribute positively to students' self-control, effort, teamwork, and overall engagement in school (Gould & Carson, 2008; Petitpas et al., 2004). The results of the study indicate that the SPS demonstrates strong potential in fulfilling its mandate of developing holistically trained student-athletes. One of the major strengths identified is the presence of highly qualified teachers and trainers who implement multidisciplinary sports training, enabling students to enhance both athletic competence and personal discipline. These strengths position the program as capable of producing well-prepared graduates who can balance sports participation with academic responsibilities. However, the study also revealed significant challenges that affect program sustainability. Notably, the lack of adequate sports facilities emerged as a major weakness that limits effective training and negatively influences student retention. This constraint has contributed to students transferring to other schools with more complete facilities, thereby affecting enrollment continuity. In conclusion, while the SPS is effective in promoting positive youth development and athletic growth, addressing infrastructural limitations is crucial to maximizing its impact. Strengthening facilities and resources, alongside sustaining instructional quality, will enhance the program's ability to meet its objectives and support the school's goal of delivering quality education.

Recommendations

The researchers recommended that further quantitative and qualitative studies should be conducted to assess the Special Program in Sports. Also, to determine the internal and external factors affecting the implementation of Special Program in Sports and to determine if the Proposed Enhancement development plan is successful or in need of re- assessment.

The researchers highly recommended to utilize the proposed Enhancement Development Plan as basis for improving and empowering the Special Program in Sports which can be utilized not only by the teachers and students of Koronadal National Comprehensive High School SPS but also by other teachers and students in other programs as there basis for enhancement.

Table 2. A proposed Enhancement Development Plan

Database	Objectives	Activities	Persons Involved	Source of fund	Budget	Time Frame	Success Indicators
Strengthening partnership with LGU for continuous	To strengthen the partnership between	Training Workshops	LGU and Coaches				Qualified Athletes as Trainers

improvement of athletes.	LGU's to continuously improve the athletes.						
Coaching seminars intensification for teachers who are coaching.	To intensify the teachers ability to coach.	Training Workshops Before Athletic Meet	DepEd Officials				Highly Qualified Coaches
Maximizing stakeholders supports in the acquisition of sports equipment.	To maximize stakeholders supports and acquire sports equipment.		Teachers, Athletes and Stakeholders				Adequate Sports Equipment Strong stakeholders support
Intensification of trainings through partnership with private institutions offering Sports Scholarships	To intensify partnerships with private institutions that offers Sports Scholarships.						Intense Partnership Between Private Institution
Sports Training Intensification to Prevent students from transferring to other schools.							High Rate of SPS Graduate
Improving internal communication to the LGU's to prevent potential athletes from transferring to the other school.							High Rate of SPS Graduate
Provision of adequate sports facilities and equipment.							Adequate sports facilities and equipment.

Improving internal communication system to prevent potential athletes from transferring to other school							Clear Internal Communication Flow, High Rate of SPS Graduate
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Through this data the Researchers had come-up with the Proposed Enhance Development Plan. The development plan was a mixed of some developmental plan because some development plan are lacking one factor which is the evaluation part. This table shows the enhanced development plan created by the researchers using the result is juxtaposition as the goals in the plan.

This table also shows the activities that will be done to achieve the goals, persons involved who will play a very important role in implementing the activities, Sources of funds, Budget, and Time frame to determine when the activities will be implemented and the goals to be achieved.

Lastly this table shows the Success Indicators. This will serve as the tool for evaluating if the Goals are achieved and the used activities are successful, if the result indicators are not seen it simply means that either the goal is unachievable, or the activities needs to be changed.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The researchers ensured full compliance with ethical standards throughout the conduct of this study. Before data collection, informed consent was obtained from all respondents, and participation was strictly voluntary. The respondents were clearly informed of their right to withdraw from the study at any time without penalty. Anonymity and confidentiality were maintained by excluding any identifying information, and all data gathered were handled in accordance with the Data Privacy Act to protect respondents' personal information. The well-being of the participants was safeguarded, and no physical, psychological, or social harm resulted from their participation. The researchers declare that no conflict of interest existed in the conduct of the study. Plagiarism was strictly avoided through proper citation of sources, and objectivity was upheld to prevent bias in the interpretation of findings. The results of this research were used solely for academic and research purposes. Additionally, artificial intelligence tools were utilized only to assist in language enhancement and organization of the manuscript, with full responsibility for the content, accuracy, and interpretation of results retained by the researchers.

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